

Oxidation of ninhydrin by quinolinium dichromate (QDC) – A kinetic and mechanistic approach

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Abstract : Quinolinium dichromate (QDC) oxidation of ninhydrin has been studied spectrophotometrically, in an aqueous perchloric acid medium at constant ionic strength of $0.025 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and at 25°C . The reaction is first order in quinolinium dichromate concentration and less than unit order each in ninhydrin and H^+ ion concentrations. Increase in perchloric acid concentration accelerates the reaction rate. The main reaction products are chromium(III) and phthalic acid. Phthalic acid was identified by spot test, IR and NMR spectra. The added product chromium(III) retards the reaction rate whereas added phthalic acid did not show any significant effect on the rate of reaction. The ionic strength and dielectric constant did not have any appreciable effect on the reaction rate. On the basis of experimental results a suitable mechanism is proposed. The activation parameters were evaluated and discussed.

Keywords : Ninhydrin, quinolinium dichromate.

Ninhydrin, 1,2,3-triketo-hydrindene hydrate, Ruhemann's reagent or more systematically as 2,2-dihydroxy-1,3-indandione, has been used for the detection and estimation of amino acids, amines, peptides and amino sugars. Ninhydrin may be applied to porous surfaces in a variety of solutions to develop a latent finger and palm prints. The effects of transition metal ions on these ninhydrin reactions have been studied by several workers¹. The kinetics of oxidation of ninhydrin by bromamine-T has been reported².

The kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of chromium(VI) has been well studied, chromic acid being one of the most versatile available oxidising agents, reacting with diverse substrates. Nowadays the development of newer chromium(VI) reagents³ for the oxidation of organic substrates continues to be of interest. The reagent employed in these investigations, quinolinium dichromate (QDC), $(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{NH}^+)_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ is a useful and versatile oxidant that deserves further investigation. We are particularly interested to see the mechanism involved in the oxidation of organic substrates by this new oxidant, quinolinium dichromate (QDC). Since, the chromium exhibits different oxidation states during oxidation, such as chromium(V), chromium(IV), chromium(III) etc., the reaction involves several complexities. In this paper, we have studied the oxidation of ninhydrin by quinolinium dichromate in perchloric acid medium and arrived at a

possible mechanism.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry and product analysis : Different sets of concentrations of reactants in 0.01 mol dm^{-3} perchloric acid at constant ionic strength, 0.25 mol dm^{-3} , were kept for over 8 h at 25°C in a closed container. The unreacted oxidant in the reaction mixture was determined by measuring the absorbance at 440 nm. The reduction product of quinolinium dichromate, chromium(III) was determined by measuring its absorbance at 580 nm. The analysis showed that one mole of ninhydrin reacted with two moles of quinolinium dichromate. The observed stoichiometry is shown in eq. (1).

The oxidation product of ninhydrin, phthalic acid was identified by spot tests⁴. It was confirmed by its melting point 206°C (literature value $206\text{--}208^\circ\text{C}$) and also by IR and NMR studies. IR : $\nu(\text{cm}^{-1})$ KBr : C=O at 1688 cm^{-1} , OH at $2900, 3100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is identical with C=O and OH of phthalic acid, NMR : δ CDCl_3 : aromatic two sets 2H at 7.5 and 2H at 7.7 and OH at 11.7.

The liberated CO₂ was detected by the limewater test.

Reaction order :

The reaction order was found from log-log plots of initial rates versus concentrations at constant perchloric acid concentration (0.01 mol dm⁻³). The order with respect to quinolinium dichromate in the 4.0 × 10⁻⁴ – 4.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ concentration range was found to be unity. The order with respect to ninhydrin concentration, between 8.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ and 8.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ was found to be less than unity (0.67) (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of variation of QDC, ninhydrin and HClO₄ concentrations on the oxidation of ninhydrin by quinolinium dichromate in aqueous perchloric acid at 25 °C and *I* = 0.25 mol dm⁻³

[QDC] × 10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	[Ninhydrin] × 10 ² (mol dm ⁻³)	[HClO ₄] × 10 ² (mol dm ⁻³)	(Initial rate) × 10 ⁶ (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)
0.4	4.0	1.0	3.31
1.2	4.0	1.0	10.0
2.0	4.0	1.0	16.4
2.8	4.0	1.0	22.5
4.0	4.0	1.0	32.9
2.0	0.8	1.0	5.69
2.0	1.6	1.0	9.72
2.0	3.2	1.0	14.2
2.0	4.0	1.0	16.4
2.0	4.8	1.0	18.9
2.0	6.4	1.0	22.8
2.0	8.0	1.0	25.0
2.0	4.0	0.5	8.71
2.0	4.0	1.0	16.4
2.0	4.0	2.0	30.9
2.0	4.0	3.0	43.7
2.0	4.0	4.0	52.5
2.0	4.0	5.0	64.6
2.0	4.0	6.0	77.6

The effect of perchloric acid on the reaction was studied between 5.0 × 10⁻³ and 6.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ at constant reactant concentrations and the rate was found to increase with increase in the concentration of perchloric acid (Table 1). The order with respect to acid concentration from the plot of log (initial rate) versus log [H⁺] was found to be less than unity (0.86).

The effect of initially added products, chromium(III) and phthalic acid was studied at constant concentrations of oxidant, [QDC] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, reductant, [ninhydrin] = 2.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, acidity, [HClO₄] =

1.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ and at constant ionic strength, *I* = 0.25 mol dm⁻³. It was observed that inhibitory effect of initially added product, chromium(III) and is shown in Fig. 1. It was found that chromium(III) in the concentration ranges 1.0 × 10⁻³ – 8.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ causes a decrease in the rate. The decrease in the rate by the addition of chromium(III) attributes to the secondary kinetic salt effect⁵. Whereas a similar range of added phthalic acid, the rate does not change appreciably.

Fig. 1. Effect of added product, chromium(III) on the QDC-ninhydrin reaction in aqueous perchloric acid at 25 °C.

At constant concentrations of reactants and other conditions constant, the ionic strength was varied between 0.10 and 0.40 mol dm⁻³ by varying the concentrations of sodium perchlorate. The solvent polarity of the reaction medium was increased from 0 to 40% (v/v) by acetic acid. It was observed that, neither the ionic strength nor the dielectric constant had any significant effect on the reaction rate.

The added ions such as Cu^{II}, Fe^{II}, SO₄²⁻, NO₃⁻ did not have any significant effect on the rate, but the added Mn^{II} retards the rate of the reaction.

The rate of reaction was measured at different temperatures under conditions of [QDC] = 2.0 × 10⁻³; [ninhydrin] = 4.0 × 10⁻²; [HClO₄] = 1.0 × 10⁻²; and *I* = 0.25 mol dm⁻³. The rate increases with temperature (1.64, 2.92 and 5.01 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³ s⁻¹ at 298, 308 and 318 K respectively). Activation parameters obtained from log rate vs 1/*T* plot are : Δ*H*[‡] = 41 ± 2 kJ mol⁻¹, Δ*S*[‡] = -

$198 \pm 6 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta G^\ddagger = 102 \pm 4 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ respectively.

The reaction mixture was mixed with acrylonitrile monomer and kept for 2 h in an inert atmosphere at room temperature. On diluting with methanol turbidity appears indicating the intervention of free radicals in the reaction.

Variation of concentrations of each of the oxidant, quinolinium dichromate, substrate, ninhydrin and acid, perchloric acid, while keeping the others fixed, found that the reaction exhibits first order in oxidant, less than unit orders each in substrate and acid concentrations (Table 1). The reaction between quinolinium dichromate and ninhydrin in perchloric acid has a stoichiometry of 2 : 1. The initially added product chromium(III) retards the reaction rate which attributes to the secondary kinetic salt effect and the other product phthalic acid did not have any significant effect on the rate. The increase in the rate with increase in the hydrogen ion concentration indicates the involvement of a protonated species of quinolinium dichromate in the prior equilibrium step as observed earlier⁶. Quinolinium dichromate in the presence of acid forms a protonated species. The protonated species combines with ninhydrin to form a complex, which then decomposes in a rate-determining step to give a free radical derived from ninhydrin and the intermediate chromium(V) being generated and followed by other fast steps to give the products. The experimental results can be accommodated in terms of Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

The initiation of polymerization of acrylonitrile indicated the presence of free radical intermediate. The results suggest the formation of a complex between the protonated species of oxidant, quinolinium dichromate and substrate, ninhydrin. Such complex formation between oxidant and substrate has been observed earlier⁷.

The spectral evidence for complex formation between oxidant and substrate was obtained from the UV-vis spectrum of quinolinium dichromate and quinolinium dichromate-ninhydrin mixtures in which a bathochromic shift of 4 nm from 230 nm to 234 nm and hyperchromicity at 234 nm was observed. A new peak at 252 nm for reaction mixture was also observed. The complex formed was also proved kinetically by the non-zero intercept of the plot of $1/\text{rate}$ vs $1/[\text{ninhydrin}]$ (Fig. 2). Since the oxidation of ninhydrin by quinolinium dichromate is a

Fig. 2. Verification of rate law (2) in the form of eq (3) (conditions as in Table 1).

non-complementary reaction, it may occur by the intervention of the active chromium(IV) and chromium(V) species. The intervention of chromium(IV) is evident from the progressive rate decrease in the presence of increasing amounts of added manganese(II), the decrease reaching a limit of approximately one half of the rate found in the absence of manganese(II). Such results have also been obtained for chromium(VI) oxidation of 2-propanol in aqueous acetic acid⁸. The induced oxidation of iodide yields two equivalent of iodine for each equivalent of the inductor oxidised. In any induced oxidation, the "induction factor" is defined as the ratio of the number of equivalents of reducing agent oxidised to the number of equivalents of inductor oxidised. The induction factor for iodide oxidation is nearly two, which indicates that the active oxidizing agent is pentavalent chromium. Scheme 1 leads to the rate law (2)

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{QDC}]}{dt}$$

$$= \frac{kK_1K_2[\text{QDC}][\text{ninhydrin}][\text{H}^+]}{1 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2[\text{ninhydrin}][\text{H}^+]} \quad (2)$$

The rate law (2) may be rearranged to eq. (3), which is suitable for verification

$$\frac{[\text{QDC}]}{\text{Rate}} = \frac{1}{kK_1K_2[\text{ninhydrin}][\text{H}^+]} + \frac{1}{kK_2[\text{ninhydrin}]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (3)$$

According to eq. (3), the plots of $[\text{QDC}]/(\text{rate})$ vs $1/[\text{ninhydrin}]$ and $[\text{QDC}]/(\text{rate})$ vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$ should be linear and are found to be so (Fig. 2).

The effect of ionic strength and solvent polarity on the rate qualitatively accounts for the reaction between an ion and a neutral molecule. The negative value of entropy of activation indicates that the complex is more ordered than the reactants. The observed modest entropy of activation suggests that the oxidation presumably occurs by an inner-sphere mechanism. This concept is supported by the results of earlier studies⁹.

Experimental

Reagent grade chemicals and double distilled water were used throughout this work. Quinolinium dichromate, QDC was prepared by the known method¹⁰ and characterized by IR and NMR spectra. The stock solution of the oxidant, QDC was prepared by dissolving QDC in water and its concentration was ascertained by iodometrically¹⁰. Ninhydrin (Merck) was used without further purification and aqueous solution of required strength was freshly prepared and used before each kinetic run. The chromium(III) solution was obtained by dissolving $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (B.D.H., A.R.) in water. The ionic strength and acidity were maintained constant with NaClO_4 and HClO_4 respectively.

Kinetic studies : Kinetics were followed at 25 ± 0.1 °C, unless otherwise stated. Reaction was initiated by adding quinolinium dichromate solution, containing required amounts of HClO_4 and NaClO_4 , to the ninhydrin solution. The reaction was generally followed under pseudo-first order conditions with ninhydrin in excess, by measuring the absorbance of quinolinium dichromate in the reaction mixture at 440 nm in a 1 cm cell placed in the thermostated compartment of Varian Cary-50 Bio UV-visible spectrophotometer. Application of Beer's law had

been verified earlier between 1.0×10^{-4} and 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} of quinolinium dichromate at 440 nm under the reaction conditions ($\epsilon = 380 \pm 10$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$). During the reaction one of the products chromium(III) formed retards the rate of the reaction. Hence we have calculated the initial rates from the plots of $[\text{QDC}]$ vs time by plane mirror method¹¹. The initial rates were reproducible within $\pm 5\%$.

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